

EMONET: A TRANSFORMER BASED NETWORK FOR CONVERSATIONAL EMOTION
RECOGNITION

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this dissertation to my family, whose unwavering love and support have been the cornerstone of my academic journey. Their sacrifices and encouragement have fuelled my determination to pursue excellence in the field of machine learning and artificial intelligence. I extend my heartfelt gratitude to my mentor, Dr R Bharathi, whose wisdom, guidance, and unwavering support have been invaluable throughout this research endeavour. This work is a testament to the dedication and resilience of my family, the mentorship of Dr R Bharathi, and the academic environment provided by LJMU. May this research contribute to the advancement of knowledge in the field and inspire future researchers to explore new frontiers in machine learning and AI.

ABSTRACT

EmoNet, an Emotion Recognition in Conversation system (ERC) aims to detect the emotional state conveyed by each utterance within a dialogue. This is a task that holds compelling application prospects across various fields. In this research, we propose Speaker Behavior modelling and Global Speaker Identity and Weighted loss function for the class imbalance dataset in ERC, a sliding window implementation in case to limit compute and memory for the Speaker Behavior module. Here we introduce a transformer-specific framework to attempt ERC in text conversation. With EmoNet, we Accurate recognition of emotion will make the related application efficient and more empathic towards its user.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

BERT: Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers

CNN: Convolutional Neural Network

COM: Context Embedding Module

GRU: Gated Recurrent Unit

KET: Knowledge-Enriched Transformer for Emotion Detection in Textual Conversations

ML: Machine Learning

NLP: Natural Language Processing

PLM: Pre-trained Language Model

PM: Pre-trained Memory

RoBERTa: Robustly Optimized BERT Pretraining Approach

SOTA: state-of-the-art

RNN: Recurrent Neural Network

RGAT: Relation-aware Graph Attention Networks with Relational Position Encodings for Emotion Recognition in Conversations

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

The ERC has emerged as a vital and dynamic frontier in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). This burgeoning interest stems from ERC's capability to analyze and understand emotions in dialogues, which is crucial for a wide array of applications. The ERC not only enriches the understanding of human-machine interactions but also lays the groundwork for advancements in various domains, including customer service, mental health, and educational technology. The increasing focus on ERC in research highlights its potential to enhance the emotional intelligence of machines, thereby revolutionizing the way we interact with technology. The integration of ERC in NLP represents a significant leap towards creating more empathetic and responsive AI systems, underscoring its importance in the ongoing evolution of artificial intelligence

Emotion Recognition in textual Conversation is a complex domain due to the interplay of semantics, context, and speaker nuances. While models like SACL Hu et al., 2023 and EmotionIC Liu et al., 2023 have made strides, there's potential in Transformer-based networks for ERC. This research introduces "EmoNet" aiming to harness this potential. EmoNet seeks to combine the strengths of previous models with the power of Transformer architectures. The goal is to capture emotional dynamics in dialogues more effectively, setting new benchmarks in ERC. This thesis endeavours to optimize ERC, offering a comprehensive solution for conversational emotion recognition.

1.2 Problem Statement

The goal of ERC is to identify the specific emotion expressed in each utterance from a set of predefined emotions. The topic of conversation, the personality of the interlocutor, viewpoint, intent and argumentation logic govern this conversation.

Emotion Recognition in conversations is a useful building block for various fields, like, psychological analysis in healthcare systems, opinion mining for social media platform data, understanding student mindsets in education, generating emotion-aware dialogue for customer

support, etc. Hence, a lack of good ERC leads to insufficient emotional modelling resulting in a lack of contextual information. This could lead to overconfidence and hard failure in the field.

1.3 Aim & Objectives

This research aims to find a method to better predict emotion in conversation. The identification of ERC is important for developing empathetic machines in areas like social opinion mining, health care, emotion-aware dialogues, and others.

Objectives:

- To fine-tune the existing pre-train language model with the conversation data set (EmoryNLP) as a base for the ERC determination.
- To run the model and evaluate the performance of the classifier based on the framework.
- To explore auxiliary tasks like self and inter-speaker dependency, contextual information for past and future, and emotion shift prediction in a Multi-Task-Learning (MTL) model.
- To arrive at a new MTL framework to explore the possibility of improving emotion recognition in conversation.
- To measure the accuracy and weighted F1 score of the model.

1.4 Research Questions

The existing best State-of-the-art (SOTA) model for Emoting Recognition in Conversation on the EmoryNLP dataset has a weighted F1 score of 41.39. Hence this research targets the following research questions:

- How can we improve the performance of emotion recognition models in conversation beyond the current state-of-the-art?
- What novel architectures or techniques can be explored to enhance emotion recognition accuracy on conversation datasets like EmoryNLP?

- Are there specific aspects of conversation data that existing models fail to capture adequately, and how can we address these limitations to achieve higher accuracy?
- What are the potential limitations or biases in the existing state-of-the-art model for emotion recognition in conversation, and how can these be addressed?
- How do different preprocessing techniques, such as data augmentation or feature engineering, impact the performance of emotion recognition models on conversation datasets like EmoryNLP?

1.5 Scope of the Study

Below is the scope of the research work:

- This research considers only textual information. Other modalities like acoustic, and visual information are not part of this research work.
- There are many datasets available of textual conversation for emotion recognition. Our choice of data set is EmoryNLP. All our experiments focus only on the EmoryNLP dataset.
- We are developing categorical models to classify emotion into a given number of discrete categories supported by the dataset.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study has the potential to contribute to the existing body of knowledge in recognizing emotion in textual-only conversation. ERC has a wide range of use cases ranging from Mental Health analysis, customer service improvement, educational tools, immersive and interactive entertainment and gaming, market research & consumer behaviour analysis and many more. The accurate recognition of emotion can make computers more precise in dealing with the response to the conversation hence avoiding hard stops in the corresponding applications in production.

1.7 Structure of the Study

The structure of the thesis is as follows. Chapter One represents the background of the research. Deep learning, development, comparison whatever you are doing. We are discussing the problem statement in section 1.2. while we are discussing the aim and objectives in section 1.3. significant of the study and this and that. Its a two to three-line description about what is the content of each of the chapters.

The structure of the study is as follows:

- Chapter 1 – Introduction: This chapter provides an introduction and background for this research work.
- Chapter 2 – Literature Review: This chapter mentions the related works in the fields of Emotion Recognition in Conversation.
- Chapter 3 – Methodology: This chapter gives a detailed walkthrough of the methodology followed during the experimentation stage.
- Chapter 4 – Implementation: This chapter details the different experiments performed for the story generation task.
- Chapter 5 – Results: This chapter discusses the results of the experiments performed in Chapter 4.
- Chapter 6 – Conclusion: This chapter concludes the work done in the thesis and discusses future improvements

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Introduction is what is the content of the chapter.

Then summarize what's been said in the chapter. A half page each. You are free to design your section and define heading subheading according to your topic.

2.1 Related Work

Hazarika, Poria, Mihalcea, et al., no date proposed ICON incorporate self and inter-speaker influences in a dialogue. Majumder et al., 2018 use context in previous utterances and emotion behind the preceding utterances and update the speaker status. Ghosal et al., 2019 developed a graph representation of a conversation and then applied a Graph Convolutional Neural Network (GCNN) to transform the task of classifying emotions in the conversation into a problem of classifying nodes within the graph. Ghosal et al., 2020 use common sense feature extraction to learn the interactions. Shen et al., 2020 developed a neural network based on a directed acyclic graph (DAG) for utterance encoding. Chen et al., 2023 propose speaker dynamic tracking to track local and global speaker states during emotional flow in conversation.

2.2 Introduction

Emotion Recognition in Conversation has achieved a big improvement in the recent past, and this continues to be a hot subject of research among academia and industry. The reason for this continued interest is due to its widespread use cases, be it human-machine interactions, empathic responses in chatbots for various industries, opinion mining in social media texts, etc. We observed that emotion recognition in textual conversation evolved through a lexicon-based approach, to Machine Learning in the previous decade. The research interest is gradually taken over by Deep Learning and Hybrid approaches.

2.3 SOTA Architectures Review

We aim through this research find a method to better predict emotion in textual conversation. Hence, it is important to understand the existing best-performing architectures. The

straightforward way to do this is to review the current state-of-the-art concerning the dataset. Below are the state-of-the-art listed against the EmoryNLP dataset.

2.3.1 KET (Knowledge-Enriched Transformer for Emotion Detection in Textual Conversations)

KET (Zhong, Wang and Miao, 2019) believe that humans often rely on context and commonsense knowledge to express emotion. KET uses hierarchical self-attention to interpret contextual utterances and context-aware affective graph attention mechanism for commonsense knowledge. It uses relatedness and affectiveness to compute the weight for the concept representation to find the context-aware affective graph. The model achieved an impressive performance jump of 0.0119 from the best-performing models of the time.

The use of a Transformer for emotion detection was brought in the first time in KET and it is more efficient in extracting contextual information from gated RNNs and CNNs. Also, their extensive experiments demonstrated that contextual information and common-sense knowledge are beneficial to emotion detection performance.

2.3.2 Relation-aware Graph Attention Networks with Relational Position Encodings for Emotion Recognition in Conversations

RGAT(Ishiwatari *et al.*, no date) considers self and inter-speaker dependencies in conversation but does not take sequential information into account. Relational position encoding in RGAT proposes to fill this gap in RGAT. Here relational positional encoding focuses on relation types to model self and interspeaker dependency. This is in contrast to encoding absolute position features and relative position features to utterances and relationships.

2.3.3 Multi-Task Learning with Auxiliary Speaker Identification for Conversational Emotion Recognition

(Xu *et al.*, 2023) work see CER as a sequence labelling problem that consider Speaker Information (SI) is highly helpful for emotion recognition in the text. Specifically, the last utterance of a speaker gives an important hint for the current utterance of the speaker.

The main component of the model is a hierarchy encoder which takes the input utterance sequence and the output of the encoder is fed into a standard emotion classification. The hierarchy encoder consists of two layers of encoder. At lowest layer contains individual utterance encoders. This uses a BERT, Bi-GRU and attention over the individual utterances. Next is the contextual utterance encoder which a Bi-GRU applied on top of the output of the individual utterance encoder as a contextual utterance encoder.

2.3.4 DialogXL: All-in-One XLNet for Multi-Party Conversation Emotion Recognition

DialogXL(Shen *et al.*, 2020) is a pioneering effort in bringing pre-trained language models for ERC. DialogXL is an improvement of XLNet, as the author believes that organizing conversational utterances as hierarchical structures is not conducive to pre-trained language models. DialogXL introduces utterance recurrence to utilize historical utterances in place of segment recurrence in XLNet. This stores hidden states of historical utterances in a memory bank reuses which identifies a query utterance. Along with this change, a dialogue self-attention introduced for local, global, speaker and listener self-attention are introduced. The outputs of the four types of self-attention are concatenated and passed through a normalization layer followed by a feed-forward network to generate the output for this transformer layer. This self-attention helps inter and intra-speaker dependencies under different reception fields in the historical context.

2.3.5 Graph Based Network with Contextualized Representations of Turns in Dialogue (TUCORE-GCN)

The TUrn COntext awaRE Graph Convolutional Network (TUCORE-GCN)(Lee and Choi, no date) is modelled by paying attention to the way people understand dialogues. The dialogue-based relation extraction aims to identify semantic relations between utterances in a dialogue.

TUCORE-GCN mimics how people understand the dialogue to address the challenges in effective relation extraction from dialogue. The speaker who speaks which utterance matters. Also, it is important to know the meaning of neighboring turns to understand the meaning of the current turn. It is important to learn multi-turn information to capture the relation between two arguments. This paper aims to tackle the above challenges.

The model uses SA-BERT(speaker-aware BERT) to encode speaker information. Masked multi-head attention with a surrounding turn mask is used to extract each turn from encoded input sequences. Then TUCORE-GCN constructs a heterogeneous dialogue graph to capture relational information between arguments in the dialogue. It constructs a dialogue node, turns node, subject node, object node and three different types of edges – speaker edge, dialogue edge and argument edge. It uses BiLSTM to turn nodes for turn-aware representation and GCN for heterogeneous dialogue graphs.

2.3.6 HiTrans: A Transformer-Based Context- and Speaker-Sensitive Model for Emotion Detection in Conversations

This(Li *et al.*, no date) is a transformer-based context and speaker-sensitive model for EDC. The architecture is a hierarchical structure of a transformer with a lower layer transformer capturing the local utterance representation and a higher-level transform capturing the global context of the conversation. On top of the model, a multilevel perceptron is used to determine the emotion. Along with this model, there is an auxiliary task called pairwise utterance speaker verification (PUSV) for speaker identification. A biaffine classifier helps here to identify two utterances belonging to the same speaker.

The model gives a performance score of 36.75 which is around one per cent higher than the existing state-of-the-art models for the time.

2.3.7 CoMPM: Context Modeling with Speaker's Pre-trained Memory Tracking for Emotion Recognition in Conversation

CoMPM(Lee and Lee, 2021) combines dialogue context with pre-trained memory from a pre-trained language model as external knowledge for improved performance in emotion recognition.

CoMPM combines speakers' pre-trained memory with the context model and finds that pre-trained memory significantly improves the performance of the context model.

The model consists of two modules. The first module is the context embedding module (COM), which takes all previous utterances as context and predicts the current emotion through attention between the previous utterances of the conversation and the current utterance. The second module which is the pre-trained memory model (PM) extracts memory from utterances.

CoM catches the underlying effect of all previous utterances on the current speakers' emotions. Hence the context model is the relationship between current and previous speech.

2.4 Summary

We have done a literature review of current state-of-the-art (SOTA) research papers for Emotion recognition in textual conversation that are listed against the EmoryNLP dataset. The attempt was specifically to understand various architecture introduced in this paper to derive new ideas or improvise the existing architecture if there is a possibility in that direction. After going through the SOTA architecture, we have selected CoMPM as a reference architecture.

CHAPTER 3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The methodology utilized in EmoNet for detecting emotions in textual conversations incorporates a multidisciplinary approach, integrating methodologies from Natural Language Processing (NLP), Machine Learning (ML), psychology, and linguistics. This approach involves several fundamental stages that are grouped as data, model, training, interpretation/evaluation, and tools.

- **Data:** In the data section, we examine methodologies for collecting data. We analyze the collected data to understand its format, structure, and information useful for ERC. We do explore relevant linguistic features and extract the same. We do see any transformation need, and evaluate class distribution in the multi-class data.
- **Model:** In the model section, we first define certain key concepts, which are specific to the problem addressed in this study. These concepts are Global Speaker Identity, Utterance History, Sliding Window, Dialogue, Context, and Context Speaker. Then we move on to the EmoNet architecture overview, define the problem we address, and the modules in the architecture: Dialogue Context (Dicon) and Speaker Behavior (SB). Next, we explore algorithms used for motion prediction algorithm, loss function, and optimization.
- **Training:** In the training section, we examine the approach followed for training the model, interface, and hyperparameters provided in EmoNet.
- **Interpretation/Evaluation:** In this section, we define the evaluation metric. Also, we interpret the result of the training, dev, and testing.
- **Tools:** In the tools section, we assess the software and hardware requirements for executing this research work.

3.2 Research Methodology

3.2.1 Data

Everything related to data in this research is explained in this section.

3.2.1.1 Data Selection

The dataset used for this study is a benchmark dataset from the EmoryNLP research group called Character-Mining Data. This dataset is derived from the transcripts of a popular TV show called Friends. The transcripts for all 10 seasons of the show with manual annotation.

The annotation for the transcripts is based on the primary emotions in the Feeling Wheel (Willcox, 1982)

Below are the episodes used for training, development, and evaluation sets:

Train (TRN)	s01_e02, s01_e03, s01_e04, s01_e05, s01_e06, s01_e07, s01_e08, s01_e09, s01_e11, s01_e12, s01_e13, s01_e14, s01_e16, s01_e17, s01_e18, s01_e19, s01_e21, s01_e22, s01_e23, s01_e24, s02_e01, s02_e02, s02_e03, s02_e04, s02_e05, s02_e06, s02_e07, s02_e09, s02_e11, s02_e12, s02_e13, s02_e14, s02_e15, s02_e16, s02_e17, s02_e18, s02_e19, s02_e21, s02_e22, s02_e24, s03_e02, s03_e03, s03_e04, s03_e05, s03_e06, s03_e07, s03_e10, s03_e11, s03_e12, s03_e13, s03_e14, s03_e15, s03_e16, s03_e17, s03_e18, s03_e19, s03_e22, s03_e23, s03_e24, s03_e25, s04_e03, s04_e04, s04_e05, s04_e07, s04_e08, s04_e09, s04_e11, s04_e12, s04_e13, s04_e14, s04_e15, s04_e16, s04_e18, s04_e19, s04_e22, s04_e23, s04_e24
Development (DEV)	s01_e15, s01_e20, s02_e10, s02_e20, s03_e01, s03_e09, s03_e21, s04_e01, s04_e06, s04_e10, s04_e21
Evaluation (TST)	s01_e01, s01_e10, s02_e08, s02_e23, s03_e08, s03_e20, s04_e02, s04_e17, s04_e20

The dataset contains 9,934 training utterances from 713 scenes, 1,344 development utterances from 99 scenes, and 1328 utterances from 85 scenes.

The primary emotions in the Feeling Wheel are sad, mad, scared, powerful, peaceful, joyful, and neutral. Each utterance is annotated with one of these seven emotions.

3.2.1.2 Data Pre-processing

The data is available in JSON format. Given below in the figure is the structure of the data set.

```

{
  "season_id": "trn",
  "episodes": [
    {
      "episode_id": "s01_e02",
      "scenes": [
        {
          "scene_id": "s01_e02_c01",
          "utterances": [
            {
              "utterance_id": "s01_e02_c01_u001",
              "speakers": ["Monica Geller"],
              "transcript": "What you guys don't understand is, for us, kissing is as important as any part of it.",
              "tokens": [
                ["What", "you", "guys", "do", "n't", "understand", "is", ",", "for", "us", ",", "kissing", "is", "as", "important", "as", "any", "part", "of", "it", "."]
              ],
              "emotion": "Joyful"
            },
            {
              "utterance_id": "s01_e02_c01_u002",
              "speakers": ["Joey Tribbiani"],
              "transcript": "Yeah, right!.....Y'serious?",
              "tokens": [
                ["Yeah", ",", "right", "!"],
                ["....."],
                ["Y'serious", "?"]
              ],
              "emotion": "Neutral"
            },
            {
              "utterance_id": "s01_e02_c01_u003",
              "speakers": ["Phoebe Buffay"],
              "transcript": "Oh, yeah!",
              "tokens": [
                ["Oh", ",", "yeah", "!"]
              ],
              "emotion": "Joyful"
            }
          ],
        }
      ],
    }
  ],
}

```

The description of the individual parameter is given in the below table.

Table 3-1 Dataset Metadata

Variable Name	Description
“season_id”	Indicates whether the data set is for training, development, or testing purposes.
“episodes”	Refers to the episodes of the TV show.
“episode_id”	Identifies a specific episode of the TV show.
“scenes”	Represents the scenes within a specific episode.
“scene_id”	Uniquely identifies each scene in the TV show.
“utterances”	Refers to the spoken lines within a specific scene.
“utterance_id”	Identifies each spoken line within a scene.
“speakers”	Represents the individuals or characters speaking the utterances.

“transcript”	Refers to the written text of the spoken lines.
“tokens”	Represents the individual words or elements within the transcript.
“emotion”	Indicates the emotional content or sentiment associated with the utterances.

3.2.1.3 Variables and Features

In this study, the author needs the “speaker”, “transcript”, and “emotion” variables from the data set for training, development, and testing of the EmoNet. The “speaker” represents the individual or character speaker of the utterances. The “transcript refers to the written text of the spoken lines. The “emotion” is the label indicating the emotional content associated with the utterances.

3.2.1.4 Data Transformation

The “speaker”, “transcript”, and “emotion” data are extracted from the data set for providing input to the training, development, and testing of the model-building process.

The above-mentioned data fields are extracted from the JSON files from the dataset. The output of this extracted data is stored in a text format. Each line represents components of an utterance. Each field in the line is separated by a vertical tab. The dialogues are separated by an empty line.

```

34 Rachel Green Oh! I see. And I've sort of been maintaining my amateur status so that I can waitress in
the Olympics. Mad
35 Chandler Bing You know, I don't mean to brag, but I waited tables at Innsbruck in '76. Amouz-bouche?
Joyful
36
37 Celia Talk to me. Neutral
38 Ross Geller OK.... um, a weird thing happened to me on the train this morning... Scared
39 Celia No no no. Talk... dirty. Joyful
40 Ross Geller Wha... what, here? Scared
41 Celia Yes... Neutral
42 Ross Geller Ah.... Neutral
43 Celia Say something..... hot. Neutral
44 Ross Geller Er.... um..... Scared
45 Celia What? Neutral
46 Ross Geller Um... uh.... vulva. Joyful
47
48 Chandler Bing Well? Neutral
49 Phoebe Buffay Wow! It's huge! It's so much bigger than the cubicle. Oh, this is a cube. Joyful
50 Chandler Bing Look at this! Joyful
51 Phoebe Buffay Oh! You have a window! Joyful
52 Chandler Bing Yes indeedy! With a beautiful view of... Joyful
53 Phoebe Buffay Oh look! That guy's peeing! Joyful
54 Chandler Bing OK, that's enough of the view. Check this out, look at this. Sit down, sit down.
Joyful
55 Phoebe Buffay OK. Neutral
56 Chandler Bing This is great! Helen, could you come in here for a moment? Powerful
57 Chandler Bing Thank you Helen, that'll be all. Neutral
58 Chandler Bing Last time I do that, I promise. Mad
59
60 Monica Geller Wendy, we had a deal! Yeah, you promised! Wendy! Wendy! Wendy! Mad
61 Rachel Green Who was that? Neutral
62 Monica Geller Wendy bailed. I have no waitress. Mad
63 Rachel Green Oh... that's too bad. Bye bye. Neutral
64 Monica Geller Ten dollars an hour. Neutral
65 Rachel Green No. Neutral
66 Monica Geller Twelve dollars an hour. Neutral
67 Rachel Green Mon. I wish I could, but I've made plans to walk around. Neutral
68 Monica Geller You know, Rachel, when you ran out of your wedding, I was there for you. I put a roof
over your head, and if that means nothing to you... twenty dollars an hour. Scared
69 Rachel Green Done. Neutral
70

```

Here, line number 37 represents the first utterance of a dialogue/scene, separated by an empty line from the previous dialogue/scene. Line number 46 represents the last utterance of the dialogue/scene followed by an empty line to separate the utterances for the next dialogue.

3.2.1.5 Class Balancing

The figure below shows the distribution of emotions in the dataset for training, development and testing respectively.

Figure 1 Class Distribution in Train, Dev, and Test Dataset

As we can see in the figure above, the data is not perfectly in balance. The training dataset contains 3,043 neutral utterances and emotion sad contains 672 utterances. The least occurring emotion data is nearly a quarter of the most occurring emotion data in the training data set.

The dialogue is a sequence of utterances in nature, one utterance after another. The emotion in the current utterance is influenced by the previous utterances in the dialogue. Hence, augmenting the data to balance the classes would influence the context of the dialogue. This could dilute the context and cause the natural transition of emotion during the dialogue. Hence the author decided to not augment as well as remove some utterances to balance the class.

3.2.2 Model

Everything related to the model in this research is explained in this section. We introduce certain terminologies to build the context of this research topic. Then we introduce the architecture of the model. These terminologies are explained below.

3.2.2.1 Global Speaker Identity

A unique identifier is given to each speaker in the conversation. This identifier is unique across the entire dataset. This is a uniformly increasing number starting from zero. As and when new

speakers appear in the dataset, the next available number is given to the speaker. When the same speaker appears next time, we reuse the number given to the speaker earlier.

3.2.2.2 Utterance History

The utterances that appear in the dataset corresponding to each speaker are captured against the speaker's name. These utterances are captured in the order they appear during the dataset loading. This will act as utterance history.

When a new utterance is processed by the system, the utterance history provides an understanding of the previous utterances from the current speaker. This helps us to understand the speaker's behaviour and to some extent the personality of the speaker.

3.2.2.3 Sliding Window

A sliding window with a configurable window size is introduced for utterance history. This enables an informed decision on memory and processing usage while maintaining utterance history.

3.2.2.4 Dialogue

A dialogue is a set of utterances (conversations) between speakers(characters) in a scene. Each line in the dataset contains <speaker>/t<utterance>/t<emotion> representing the name of the speaker, the utterance (spoken text) made by the speaker, and the primary emotion conveyed in the utterance.

Dialogues are demarcated by an empty line (\n) in the dataset. In the context of the ERC task, there is no need to maintain the other details like episodes and scene ID. But, for this research work, we maintain the same order of utterances and dialogues, as it appears in the data source, ignoring other metadata for the dataset. There is no shuffling made to make it random, as maintaining the sequence of conversation is important to the nature of the task.

3.2.2.5 Context

The context represents the context of the utterance. The context of the utterance is a list of all the utterances in the order they happened in the current dialogue. This means at the beginning of a dialogue; the context contains only the utterance made by the first speaker in the dialogue. Also, at the end of the dialogue, the context contains all the utterances that happened in the dialogue. The context gets reset at the beginning of each dialogue.

3.2.2.6 Context Speaker

Similar to the context, the context speaker represents the speakers in the context. It is a list of global speaker IDs corresponding to the speaker of the utterance in the order it appeared in the dialogue. At the beginning of a dialogue, the context speaker contains only the ID of the current speaker. At the end of the dialogue, the context speaker contains IDs corresponding to the speaker of each utterance in the dialogue. A speaker ID can appear multiple times in the context speaker list if there are multiple utterances made by the speaker in the dialogue. The context speaker gets reset at the beginning of each dialogue.

3.2.2.7 Architecture Overview

The EmoNet is composed of two modules. The first module is called Dialogue Context embedding (DiCon). This captures the underlying effect of all previous utterances in the current dialogue on the current speaker's emotion. The second module is Speaker Behaviour (SB), which tracks the current speaker's historical utterances in current dialogues as well as all previous dialogues.

Figure 2 EmoNet Architecture

This model consists of two modules: a Dialogue context embedding module and a Speaker behaviour module. The figure shows an example of predicting emotion of u_6 , from a 6-turn dialogue context. A, D, and Y refer to the participant in the conversation, where $S_A = S_{u1} = S_{u4} = S_{u6}$, $S_D = S_{u2}$, and $S_Y = S_{u3} = S_{u5}$. W_o and W_p are linear matrices

3.2.2.8 Task overview

A dialogue with N sequential utterances are represented as $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_N\}$ with corresponding speakers $S = \{s_{u1}, s_{u2}, \dots, s_{uN}\}$ and emotion label $E = \{e_{u1}, e_{u2}, \dots, e_{uN}\}$. Here, speakers S_{u_i} and S_{u_j} for the utterances u_i and u_j , where $i \neq j$ can be the same. The model objective is to correctly predict the emotion e_t for the t^{th} utterance u_t , by using the previous utterances and speaker information along with u_t and s_{u_t} .

3.2.2.9 DiCon

The dialogue context embedding module embeds the utterances and speaker of the utterances in a dialogue to help predict the emotion e_t of the current utterances u_t . The example in Figure x shows how this module contributes to the prediction of emotion e_6 uttered by S_A . Here, the conversation has three participants (S_A , S_D , S_Y). Here, S_A spoke for u_1 , u_3 , and u_6 , S_D spoke u_2 and S_Y spoke u_2 and u_4 .

A special token is used to distinguish the speaker from the utterance. For example, in the above figure, input to the embedding would be $\langle sS_A \rangle u_1 \langle sS_D \rangle u_2 \dots \langle sS_A \rangle u_6$. Here S_A and S_D are replaced by the global speaker identifier of speaker A, u_1 , u_2 , .. u_6 are replaced with text spoken in corresponding utterances.

A special token $\langle \text{cls} \rangle$ is used to predict the emotion. The special token is prefixed at the input. The output of the model is as follows:

$$c_t = \text{DiCon}(\langle \text{cls} \rangle, S_{:t}, U_{:t})$$

Where $S_{:t}$ is the set of speakers including current speakers in the dialogue. $U_{:t}$ is the sequence of utterances including current utterances in the dialogue. $c_t \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times h_c}$ and h_c is the dimension of DiCon

3.2.2.10 Speaker Behaviour

The current speaker's behaviour is modelled using the speaker's historical utterances across all previous dialogues. For example, in Figure 1, the present dialogue contributes u_1 , u_3 , and u_6 to the historical utterances as the last three entries. A special token $\langle \text{cls} \rangle$ is prefixed in front of each utterance. The output of the model is as follows:

$$k_i = \text{SB}(\langle \text{cls} \rangle, u_i)$$

Where $S_{ui} = S_{ut}$ where S_{ut} is the speaker of the current utterance. $c_t \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times h_k}$ and h_k is the dimension of Speaker Behaviour.

The significance of each k_i depends on the distance of the utterance from the current utterance. This k_i tracking is done using GRU. This tracking is done using a unidirectional GRU:

$$k_t = \text{GRU}(k_{i1}, k_{in}, \dots, k_{in})$$

where t is the turn index of the current utterance, $n = \min(\text{window size, the number of utterances historically made by the speaker})$. The number of utterances could grow very large depending on the dataset. Hence to limit the compute and memory usage, a configurable window size can be used. $k_t \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times h_c}$ is the output of k_{in} and as a result, the knowledge of distant utterance is diluted and the effect on the current utterance is reduced.

The output of GRU is represented as:

$$O_t = c_t + W_p(k_{tt})$$

Here, W_p represents a matrix that projects the pre-trained memory to the dimension of the context output.

3.2.2.11 Emotion Prediction

We use the softmax function on O_t multiplied by W_o of dimension $\mathbb{R}^{h_e \times h_c}$ to generate a probability distribution over emotion classes. Here, h_e represents the number of emotion classes.

$$P(e) = \text{softmax}(W_o \cdot o_t)$$

The predicted emotion class e_t corresponds to the index of the highest probability in the emotion class distribution.

3.2.2.12 Loss function

As we see in section 3.2.1.5 Class Balancing, the dataset is not properly balanced. Hence, we need to adjust this class imbalance by assigning higher weights to the minority class and lower weights to the majority class.

3.2.2.13 Optimization

The optimization algorithm we use is AdamW (Yao et al., 2021) with a learning rate of 1e-8, eps value 1e-06m, and weight_decay value of 0.01.

3.2.3 Training

EmoNet follows the batch training approach to allow efficient memory utilization, speedy computation, stable optimization, and scalability. The default batch size is one. That is each turn in the data set is considered as a batch. As explained in section 3.2.2.4 and section 3.2.2.5, the speaker, utterance, and label are used to build dialogue context, and speaker behaviour.

We support the following hyperparameters:

- --batch: Number of data points per batch; default 1
- --epoch: Number of iterations made during the training.; default 10
- --lr: learning rate; default 1e-6

To start the training use the below command:

```
Python train.py
```

3.2.4 Interpretation/Evaluation

The standard metric used to evaluate the model for this multi-class classification problem is the weighted F1 score.

After completing each epoch, we run the model on the dev dataset to measure the weighted F1 score. Once we see the current weighted F1 score of the dev dataset is better than the past run, we select this weighted F1 score as the best score available. Also, save the model as a reference.

Once the training is completed, we have the model with the best dev dataset weighted F1 score. We load the model corresponding to this Epoch and measure the weighted F1 score of the test dataset.

3.3 Logical flow of the system

As we see in the above section, the end-to-end system can be visualized in the diagram below.

Figure 3 End-to-End Solution Framework

We have raw data from the EmoryNLP repository. This static data is in the form of JSON files. This contains a file for train, a file for dev, and a file test dataset. We do a manual download of these data files.

We do parse this JSON to select only the needed feature and the label. The output of this stage is a text file with speaker, utterance, and emotion labels separated by a vertical tab. Each line represents a turn in the conversation. A set of consecutive turns makes a dialogue. An empty line demarks two dialogues.

We do parse, these features. During parsing, we build dialogue context, personal history and Speaker History context as explained above. We use a tokenizer to tokenize this dialogue context and the personal history of the current speaker. A data loader takes a batch of single turns at a time. The Data loader inputs this batch to EmoNet.

EmoNet trains this input and generates inferences. After completing a configured number of epochs, it selects the best dev output as model output.

This model output is used to test the test dataset to find the model performance.

3.4 Tools

Software and Hardware requirements are as follows:

3.4.1 Software requirements

- Python programming language, starting from version 3.8 and above.
- Pytorch, with a minimum requirement of version 1.0.
- Scikit-learn, version 1.0.3 or higher.
- Matplotlib, ideally version 3.7.1 or newer.
- Seaborn, starting from version 0.11.2.
- Pandas, version 2.0.2 or above.
- Numpy, at least version 1.24.2.
- Jupyter Notebook, version 6.1 or more

3.4.2 Hardware

- A6000 48GB GPU hosted on cloud provider

The main hardware requirement is for fine-tuning the pre-trained language model with the customized dataset.

3.5 Summary

We have gone through the methodology followed by EmoNet architecture to predict Emotion in the current turn in a conversation. We have explored the methodology followed in dealing with data, which encompasses the data source, data collection, data transformation, and feature engineering. Then, we delve into the modelling methodology. We have defined terminology specific to the problem context and introduced EmoNet architecture, and different modules in EmoNet. We looked into the loss function, optimization, prediction algorithm, etc. We then delve into the training and evaluation of the model and metric used for measuring the model performance. Finally, we have noted the software and hardware needed for this study.

CHAPTER 4 IMPLEMENTATION

4.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the details of the code-level implementation of EmoNet. The sections in the chapter are as follows:

4.2 Build Custom Dataset

We need a custom Dataset that pre-processes and prepares the data in a way Emonet expect. This will form the basis of input for the two internal modules in the architecture introduced. Both the Dialogue context embedding module and Speaker Behaviour expect a different set of inputs. These inputs are derived from the row data from the data store. Each entry in the raw data contains “<speakername>\t<utterance>\t<emotionlabel>”.

The below algorithm defines the custom dataset with an interface to access individual data sample.

```
create an instance of dataset specific to EmoryNLP data.

Initialize a global speakerID list,
Initialize an utteranceHistory dictionary with speakerName as key and list of
utterances as value.
Initialize an empty dialogue list
Open the file and read the data
For a line in dataset:
    If the line is empty:
        reset the context, and reset contextSpeaker
    Else
        collect spakerName, uttrance and emotionLabel
        add the utterance in to the context list
        If spakerName is known:
            extract speakerID from the speakerID list
        Else
            assign new speakerID and add the ID to the speakerID list
```

Add the utterance to the utterance list in the utteranceHistory dictionary corresponding to spakerName key

get the list of all utterances for the utteranceHistory dictionary for the spakerName as speakerUtteranceHistory

add a list containing contextSpeaker, context, speakerUtteranceHistory, and emotionLabel in the dialogue list as engineered details corresponding to the current utterance.

define __getitem__ method which will provide one entry from the dialogue list at a time.

4.3 Tokenizing and Loading

This step constitutes the algorithm for a helper function, which takes the dataset in batch form. Build the context model and speaker memory with special tokens and tokenize it to ready as model input.

for each entry in the dialogue:

extract the contextSpeaker, context, speakerUtteranceHistory, emotionLabel from the input

for each speakerID and utterance in contextSpeaker and context

inputString += create as string "<s"+speakerID+">"+ " "+utterance

use RoBERTa tokenizer and tokenize this inputString .

take only the last 511 tokens by using the right truncation.

converts this list of tokens into a list of corresponding token IDs

prefix this with the 'start of sequence' token id

```
for each utterance in speakerUtteranceHistory
    use RoBERTa tokenizer to tokenize
    right truncate to max 511 tokens
    convert these tokens to IDs and prefix them with "start of sequence"
    make the length of the token ID list of each utterance to same length by
padding at the end
```

4.4 Model building

The below pseudo-code describes the internal functionality of the mode.

```
Models building

we use RoBERTa model from HuggingFace Transformer library
Initialization:
INPUT: clsNum - number of classes

instantiate contextModel by loading pre-trained weights and configurations for
roberta-large.
collect the dimensionality (hiddenDim) of the hidden states for the contextModel.
This information might be crucial for defining the architecture of downstream
models or for performing computations involving the hidden states of the RoBERTa
model.

instantiate speakerModel by loading pre-trained weights and configurations for
roberta-large.
sets up initial hidden states for a GRU network
initialize the GRU network(speakerGRU) with input and hidden state sizes, number
of layers, and dropout probability
```

create a linear transformation layer(W) with input size as hiddenDim and output size as a number of classes(clsNum)

create a list of trainable parameters. the list contains parameters from contextModel, speakerGRU, and W

Define computational graph:

INPUT: batchInputTokens, batchSpeakerTokens

perform forward pass of the input batchInputTokens and collect hidden states of the last token($[:, -1, :]$ <- all dimensions of hidden states, i.e CLS token) in the input sequences after processing them through the model's layer into batchContextOutput.

for each speakerTokens in batchSpeakerTokens:

 perform forward pass of the input speakerTokens and collect hidden states of the last token($[:, -1, :]$ <- all dimensions of hidden states, i.e CLS token) in the input sequences after processing them through the model's layer into speakerOutput.

 transform the speakerOutput to 2d

 create a GRU instance with input speakerOutput and h_0 as the initial hidden state as speakerGRUOutput.

 select the last hidden state from the speakerGRUOutput as speakerTrackVector. The resulting shape is (1,hidden_size)

 This speakerTrackVector is appended to the batchSpeakerOutput.

convert this back to batch dimension; a single tensor resulting from concatenating all the tensors in the list along batch dimension as batchSpeakerOutput. The shape is (batch_size, 1024) that is (1,1024)

add the batchContextOutput and batchSpeakerOutput

use the linear transformation layer W to get the model output.

4.5 Training

The model training happens here. The below procedure invokes all the other procedures to provide the model output.

Load the dataset from datastore(files related to train , dev and test)

Create an instance of custom dataset builder

create dataloader instance

Create an instance of the model

Set the model instance to training mode

Define the optimizer with training parameters and learning rate

For the number of epoch:

 For data in dataloader:

 get the batchInputTokens, batchLabel, batchSpeakerTokens from the data

 invoke model instance to with the batchInputTokens and batchSpeakerTokens to do forward pass in training

 calculate the loss(weighted cross entropy)

 do backward pass

 do optimization step

 calculate the precision, recall, and weighted F1 score

 if the F1 score is better than earlier F1 score:

 save this as candidate F1 score and save the model

Run the saved model against the test data to get the test F1 score.

4.6 Summary

In this module, we have defined the algorithms used for the research work. For the actual code, please look at the Appendix C:

CHAPTER 5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the results of the experiments performed in Chapter 4. The results are evaluated in both a quantitative and qualitative manner:

5.2 Model Output

The EmoNet is inspired by (Lee and Lee, 2021) CoMPM, hence, testing started with running CoMPM as a base model.

The author introduced a global identity to the speaker across the dataset. This is a major change in the approach done in the base model. Earlier, the speaker's identity is unique within a dialogue and once we move from one dialogue to another dialogue, all the learnings about the speakers are lost. Hence the purpose it solves was to differentiate the utterances in a dialogue.

The global speaker identity dilutes the model output since it now needs more data so that there is enough data specific to each speaker. Also, the global speaker identity enables the model to expand its limit to all historical conversations with a special focus on current dialogue. Hence, this is an important step forward as it opens up many avenues for further improving the model.

Using the global speaker identity, we have modelled speaker behaviour/personality. Along with the context of the dialogue, the behaviour pattern influences the emotion of the speaker. We have modelled the same by tracking historical utterances across the dialogues, with a sliding window of configurable limit.

Certain emotions are more common in our conversations and others are very rare. In the EMORYNLP dataset (Zahiri and Choi, 2017), emotion labels Sad, Powerful, and Peaceful are the least occurring labels. the emotion labels Sad, Powerful, and Peaceful are the least occurring labels with a ratio of 1:4.5, 1:3.8, and 1: 3.3 respectively against the most frequent emotion

label. As the sequence of utterances in the dialogue has a high influence on the emotion of the speaker, no data manipulation techniques are employed to class balance data.

Hence introduced weights for each class label based on its frequency to finance loss value during training.

Table 5-1 Model Output

Models	Accuracy	Weighted Avg F1
Base(ComPM)	39.38	37.85
+ Global Speaker ID	35.51	29.43
+ Speaker Behavior	39.90	36.96
+ Class Weighted loss w/o normalise	40.43	37.13
+ Class Weighted loss w normalise	41.18	39.18

5.3 Interpretation of Visualizations

We have generated a confusion matrix on the most promising model. As we can see in the abut table, the model that provided the highest score is the model with normalized weighted loss & speaker behaviour model. The confusion matrix below shows the emotion labels “Neutral”, “Joy” and “Scared” are classified better. The label “Powerful” is the least misclassified.

Figure 4 Confusion Matrix on Model Output

5.4 Summary

After looking into the results of the various experiments, it is clear that modelling the speaker's behaviour based on historical utterances has a clear benefit in the performance of emotion prediction in a conversation.

CHAPTER 6 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the conclusion drawn during this research work, its contribution to the knowledge base, and future recommendations in emotion recognition in textual conversation.

6.2 Discussion and Conclusion

As we know a significant source of information that signals emotion is carried in another mode of communication. This includes but is not limited to the tonality of the speaker, facial expressions, and body language.

Let us consider conversations involve only textual mode like a text-based chatbot or conversations where only textual information is available as in the case of the EmoryNLP (Zahiri and Choi, 2017b) dataset consisting of a textual conversation of characters in the TV show. Here we do not have the luxury of accessing tonality, visual cues, and body language. We are limited to only the textual conversation and label corresponding to the text. Hence a significant portion of information is lost which could help us determine the emotion of the speaker.

The partial information carried in the utterances is a known challenge in the ERC of textual data. As we have seen in our literature review, the researchers focus mainly on the current context of the dialogue. We agree that the context of the current dialogue has a high influence on the emotion of the speaker.

To mitigate the information loss, we could supplement additional information by modelling the behavioural pattern/personality of the speaker. The pattern helps find the zone where the emotion of the speaker moves around in general. Along with the context of the current dialogue, these additional patterns help recognize the emotion of the current speaker.

The EmoNet has achieved a weighted F1 score of 39.18. As per the current state-of-the-art model scores, this holds the 8th position just behind the TUCORE_GCN_RoBERTa model. It

has achieved a +1.81-point jump from our reference model CoMPM. EmoNet is inspired by ComPM.

Table 6-1 Model Output Comparison with SOTA Architecture

Model	Dataset: EmoryNLP Score: Weighted F1	SOTA rank
InstructERC	41.39	1
TUCORE-GCN_RoBERTa	39.24	7
EmoNet	39.18	
S+PAGE	39.14	8
CoMPM (ref concept for EmoNet)	37.37	16

Source: <https://paperswithcode.com/sota/emotion-recognition-in-conversation-on-4>

6.3 Contribution to Knowledge

As stated in section 6.2, EmoNet has achieved a significant jump in the performance of the Emotion Recognition in textual Conversation dataset from its base model. In summary, our contribution to the knowledge can be as follows:

- We propose that the speaker needs global identity across all data the model is exposed to rather than the dialogue level identity. This helps the prediction based on past knowledge.
- We model Speaker Behaviour based on historical utterances. Also, propose a sliding window view of historical utterances with configurable window size as input to the speaker behaviour model.
- We propose to use Weighted Cross Entropy loss to deal with class imbalance in the dataset rather than using any data augmentation and sampling technique

6.4 Future Recommendations

The availability of Global speaker identity and speaker utterance history has opened up new possibilities to investigate. These possibilities are related to:

- Better model for participants' behaviour patterns.

- Interworking the behaviour of different participants and its influence on the emotion of the current speaker.

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CHAPTER 9 APPENDIX B : RESEARCH PROPOSAL

EMONET: A TRANSFORMER BASED NETWORK FOR CONVERSATIONAL EMOTION
RECOGNITION

Biju Puthan Veetil

Research Proposal

December 2023

Abstract

EmoNet, an Emotion Recognition in Conversation system targets to detect the emotional state conveyed by each utterance within a dialogue, a task that holds compelling application prospects across various fields. Here we introduce a transformer-specific framework to attempt ERC in text conversation. Accurate recognition of emotion will make the related application efficient and more empathic towards its user.

1. Background

The ERC has emerged as a vital and dynamic frontier in the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). This burgeoning interest stems from ERC's capability to analyze and understand emotions in dialogues, which is crucial for a wide array of applications. As a branch of sentiment analysis, ERC not only enriches the understanding of human-machine interactions but also lays the groundwork for advancements in various domains, including customer service, mental health, and educational technology. The increasing focus on ERC in research highlights its potential in enhancing the emotional intelligence of machines, thereby revolutionizing the way we interact with technology. The integration of ERC in NLP represents a significant leap towards creating more empathetic and responsive AI systems, underscoring its importance in the ongoing evolution of artificial intelligence

Emotion Recognition in textual Conversation is a complex domain due to the interplay of semantics, context, and speaker nuances. While models like SACL Hu et al., 2023 and EmotionIC Liu et al., 2023 have made strides, there's potential in Transformer-based networks for ERC. This research introduces "EmoNet," aiming to harness this potential. EmoNet seeks to combine the strengths of previous models with the power of Transformer architectures. The goal is to capture emotional dynamics in dialogues more effectively, setting new benchmarks in ERC. This thesis endeavors to optimize ERC, offering a comprehensive solution for conversational emotion recognition.

2. Problem Statement and Related Work

The goal of ERC is to identify the specific emotion expressed in each utterance from a set of predefined emotions. The topic of conversation, personality of interlocutor, view point, intent and argumentation logic govern this conversation.

2.1 Problem Statement

Emotion Recognition in conversations is a useful building block for various fields, like, psychological analysis in healthcare systems, opinion mining for social media platform data, understanding student mindsets in education, generating emotion-aware dialogue for customer support, etc. Hence, a lack of good ERC leads to insufficient emotional modelling resulting in a lack of contextual information. This could lead to overconfidence and hard failure in the field.

2.2 Related Work

Hazarika, Poria, Mihalcea, et al., no date proposed ICON incorporate self and inter-speaker influences in a dialogue. This extends Conversational Memory Network Hazarika, Poria, Zadeh, et al., no date, which evaluates the historical context of utterances to identify the relationship between speakers. Majumder et al., 2018 uses context in previous utterances and emotion behind the preceding utterances and update the speaker status. Ghosal et al., 2019 developed a graph representation of a conversation, and then apply a Graph Convolutional Neural Network (GCNN) to transform the task of classifying emotions in the conversation into a problem of classifying nodes within the graph. Ghosal et al., 2020 use common sense feature extraction to learn the interactions. Shen et al., 2020 developed a neural network based on a directed acyclic graph (DAG) for the purpose of utterance encoding. Chen et al., 2023 propose speaker dynamic tracking to track local and global speaker state during emotional flow in conversation.

3. Research Questions

The existing best State of the Art (SOTA) model for Emotion Recognition in Conversation on EmoryNLP dataset has weighted F1 score of 41.39. Can we explore and come up with better model to recognize emotions in conversation?

4. Aim & Objectives

The aim of this research is to find a method to better predict emotion in conversation. The identification of ERC important for developing empathetic machine in areas like social opinion mining, health-care, emotion aware dialogs, and others.

Objectives:

- To fine-tune the existing pre-train language model with the conversation data set (EmoryNLP) as a base for the ERC determination.
- To run the model and evaluate the performance of the classifier based on the framework.
- To explore auxiliary tasks like self and inter-speaker dependency, contextual information for past and future, and emotion shift prediction in a Multi-Task-Learning (MTL) model.
- To arrive a new MTL framework to explore the possibility of improving emotion recognition in conversation.
- To measure the accuracy and weighted F1 score of the model.

5. Significance of the Study

This study has the potential to contribute to the existing body of knowledge in recognizing emotion in textual-only conversation. ERC has a wide range of use cases ranging from Mental Health analysis, customer service improvement, educational tools, immersive and interactive entertainment and gaming, market research & consumer behaviour analysis and many more. The accurate recognition of emotion can make computers more precise in dealing with the response to the conversation hence avoiding hard stops in the corresponding applications in production.

6. Scope of the Study

Below is the scope of the research work:

- This research considers only textual information. Other modalities like acoustic, and visual information are not part of this research work.

- There are many datasets available of textual conversation for emotion recognition. Our choice of data set is EmoryNLP. All our experiments focus only on the EmoryNLP dataset.
- We are developing categorical models to classify emotion into a given number of discrete categories supported by the dataset.

7. Research Methodology

The methodology deployed involved first making a base model by fine-tuning a language model with the dataset. Then explore additional features in an iterative way to improve the performance.

The incremental model would follow the multi-task learning model approach as mentioned in Haque et al., 2022. In the process of customizing large pre-trained models for specific downstream tasks, it is often standard to fine-tune distinct models for each task. This method generally achieves high-quality results but comes with significant computational and storage demands. An alternative, more economical strategy involves incorporating modules tailored to each task into a unified pre-trained model. For instance, multi-task adapters modify models designed for single tasks to handle multiple tasks by integrating additional task-specific parameters, known as adapters.

7.1 Pre-trained Language Models

Pretrained language models (PLMs) are foundational components in contemporary natural language processing (NLP) research, especially within the domain of transformer-based models. These models are initially trained on vast corpora of text data, encompassing a diverse range of linguistic structures, vocabularies, and styles. This extensive pretraining allows PLMs to develop a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of language, capturing context, semantics, and syntax effectively. PLMs serve as adaptable starting points for a variety of NLP tasks, from text classification to sentiment analysis.

7.2 Fine-Tuning PLM

Fine-tuning a pre-trained language model (PLM) is a pivotal step in tailoring these advanced NLP tools to specific tasks and datasets. This process begins with a PLM that has been extensively trained on large, diverse text corpora, endowing it with a broad understanding of language patterns. In fine-tuning, this general knowledge is honed to perform specific NLP tasks like sentiment analysis or text classification more effectively. This is achieved by further training the PLM on a smaller, task-specific dataset, which allows the model to adjust its pre-learned parameters to better suit the nuances of the target task.

7.3 DataSet

Below is the metadata of the dataset.

Variable Name	Description
1. utterance_id	A unique ID for each dialogue segment.
2. speakers	Lists the character(s) speaking.
3. transcript	The actual spoken text.
4. tokens	A tokenized version of the transcript, broken into words and punctuation
5. emotion	The primary emotion conveyed in the utterance.

7.4 Model Implementation

8. Required Resources

Hardware and software requirements are as follows:

8.1 Hardware requirements

Google Colab free account with hosted GPU enabled or Colab Pro.

8.2 Software requirements

- Python programming language, starting from version 3.8 and above.
- Pytorch, with a minimum requirement of version 1.0.
- Scikit-learn, version 1.0.3 or higher.
- Matplotlib, ideally version 3.7.1 or newer.
- Seaborn, starting from version 0.11.2.
- Pandas, version 2.0.2 or above.

- Numpy, at least version 1.24.2.
- Jupyter Notebook, version 6.1 or more

9. Research Plan

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CHAPTER 10 APPENDIX C: PYTHON CODE

The code implementation is available at <https://github.com/bijupv/Emonet-prework>